

Effect of Indifferent Electrolytes on Creaming of Oil-Water Emulsions Stabilized by Long Chain Ions

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Concept of equi-creaming concentration (C_E) is introduced here. It is the concentration of the creaming agent which on thorough mixing with a definite volume of the emulsion gives just a clear aqueous phase and a creamed layer after a definite period when the emulsion is allowed to stand. Creaming agents may function simultaneously or separately in two ways: (i) by building a bridge which holds a number of droplets and the resulting increase in effective radius causes the emulsion to cream; (ii) by reducing ψ_δ , the repulsive potential which prevents the close approach of charged heads and this reduction allows the droplets to come close and stick together to form aggregates which cream subsequently. The present investigation is on the determination of C_E of different inorganic electrolytes which may function as creaming agent by reducing ψ_δ to an extent not to promote coalescence but leading to strong adhesion. The results indicate that C_E depends on the valency of the counter ions and not on the amount of the stabilizing ion for a fairly stable emulsion.

It is a common experience that a sufficient excess of indifferent electrolytes can break emulsions through flocculation and coalescence though presence of small amount of an electrolyte causes creaming to take place in a relatively short period compared to that required under the influence of gravity. King and Mukherjee¹ reported analysis of the droplet size which grew up to a certain dimension and then the size remained same. According to M. Van den Tempel² the oil droplets in an aggregate are still separated by a high potential barrier having a width of the order of 100 Å or more. Coalescence can only occur owing to the breaking of the film lying in between the droplets in the aggregate. This may happen if the aggregates are allowed to stand for a sufficiently long period so that drainage of the film may occur or are subjected to mechanical distortion so that the film may break. Formation of the aggregates and the occurrence of coalescence is the net result in the reduction of ψ_δ potential which prevents close approach of the charged heads so that the oil droplets are not allowed to come close and stick together.

The concentrations of different electrolytes which can just bring about the coagulation of a definite volume of the sol in the same time have been termed equi-coagulating concentrations. Similar effects are very likely to be produced by creaming agents in an oil-water emulsion and are found so in practice. The concentrations of the creaming agents which on thorough mixing with a definite volume of the emulsion can just give a clear aqueous phase and a creamed layer in the same period when the emulsion is allowed to stand are termed equi-creaming concentrations (C_E).

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1. A. King and L. N. Mukherjee, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.* (London), 1939, 243.

2. M. Van den Tempel, *Proc. 2nd Internat. Congr. Surface Activity*, 1, 439, Butterworths, London, (1957).

The polyvalent electrolyte such as sodium alginate often used for creaming in an emulsion does not build only a bridge to hold a number of droplets together but also reduces simultaneously the repulsive potential ψ_δ . ψ_δ may also be reduced by the addition of inorganic electrolytes. The ions added may not interact with the stabilizing ion but the reduction in ψ_δ allows the droplets to come close and stick together to form aggregates. This increase in effective radius causes the emulsion to cream. The present investigation is on the determination of C_E of different electrolytes with a view to ascertain its dependence on the valency of the counter ions and on the amount of the stabilizing ion for a fairly stable emulsion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : Long chain electrolytes used as the stabilizer are cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and N-acetyl pyridinium chloride (CPyCl). Purity of these samples has been discussed in details previously^{3,4}. Double distilled water of specific conductivity $2 \times 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been used. Electrolytes such as KCl, K_2SO_4 , K_3 -citrate, NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , NaCl, Na_2SO_4 and Na_3 citrate are guaranteed reagents, E. Merck and have been used without further purification. Oils used are *n*-heptane and liquid paraffin. *n*-Heptane is the product of E. Merck and redistilled. Liquid paraffin of B.P. quality has been used without any purification.

Preparation of the emulsions : Emulsions have been prepared by hand shaking followed by homogenization by a hand operated homogenizer. Compositions of the emulsions prepared have been recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No. of emulsion	Vol. of the aqueous phase in ml.	Vol. of the oil dispersed in ml.	Oil used	Stabilizing electrolyte	Concentration of the stabilizing electrolyte in gm-mole/l. (before dispersion)
I	200 ml.	20 ml.	<i>n</i> -Heptane	CTAB	6.845×10^{-4}
II	"	"	"	"	3.539×10^{-4}
III	"	"	Liq. paraffin	CPyCl	7.46×10^{-4}
IV	"	"	"	"	3.73×10^{-4}

Rapid rate of Creaming : time 30 minutes.

Five pairs of clean and dry test tubes have been taken in a stand and marked 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. 5 ml. or less of an electrolyte have been taken in each test tube and the volumes have been made up to 5 ml. exactly with conductivity water whenever necessary. In the other series of 5 test tubes 5 ml. of emulsion have been taken. The electrolyte has first been added to the emulsion and the mixture has then been poured back into the original test tube

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TABLE II

Emulsion	Electrolyte	Blank	Equi-creaming concentration in gm.mole/l (compared to blank)
I	KCl	1.5M KCl in the aqueous phase of emulsion (I) and allowed to stand for 24 hours.	0.592
II	"	"	0.592
III	"	"	0.603
IV	"	"	0.603
I	K ₂ SO ₄	0.1M K ₂ SO ₄ in the aqueous phase of emulsion (I) and allowed to stand for 24 hours.	0.031
II	"	"	0.031
III	"	"	0.036
IV	"	"	0.036
I	K ₃ -Citrate	0.002M K ₃ -citrate in the aqueous phase of emulsion (I) and allowed to stand for 24 hours.	0.0008
II	"	"	0.0008
III	"	"	0.00082
IV	"	"	0.00082
I	NaCl	Same as for KCl	0.57
II	"	"	0.57
III	"	"	0.62
IV	"	"	0.62
I	Na ₂ SO ₄	Same as for K ₂ SO ₄	0.034
II	"	"	0.034
III	"	"	0.041
IV	"	"	0.041
I	Na ₃ -Citrate	Same as for K ₃ -citrate	0.00072
II	"	"	0.00072
III	"	"	0.00086
IV	"	"	0.00086
I	NaNO ₃	Same as for KCl	0.65
III	"	"	0.70
I	KNO ₃	"	0.63
III	"	"	0.69

which has contained the electrolyte, in order to ensure thorough mixing. The test tubes containing the mixtures have been allowed to stand undisturbed for 30 mins. 2 ml. of the aqueous phase at the bottom have then been drawn out by a syringe provided with a long needle and poured into a clean and dry test tube. Transparency of this aqueous phase compared to the blank used have been noted. Concentration of an electrolyte, which on addition to the emulsion by the above mentioned method gives just an aqueous phase having the same transparency as the blank has been noted as the equi-creaming concentration (C_E). A small increase in concentration just above C_E has produced an aqueous phase having same transparency as the blank in a relatively very short period compared to the time scheduled. A small decrease in concentration just below C_E has given an aqueous phase having prominent turbidity compared to the blank even after allowing the resulting mixture to stay for a relatively long period. C_E values of different electrolytes for each of the emulsion are recorded in the Table II.

DISCUSSION

The ratio of the equi-creaming concentrations when expressed in millimoles per litre is as follows :

	KCl.	K ₂ SO ₄	K ₃ -citrate	
Emulsion (I)	100	5.24	0.14	
Emulsion (II)	100	5.24	0.14	
Emulsion (III)	100	6.07	0.14	
Emulsion (IV)	100	6.07	0.14	
	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄	Na ₃ -citrate	
Emulsion (I)	100	5.97	0.14	
Emulsion (II)	100	5.97	0.14	
Emulsion (III)	100	6.61	0.14	
Emulsion (IV)	100	6.61	0.14	
	KCl.	KNO ₃	NaCl	NaNO ₃
Emulsion (I)	59.2	63.0	57.0	65.0
Emulsion (II)	60.3	69.0	62.0	70.0

The equi-creaming concentrations thus depend markedly on the valency of the counter ions present in the added electrolyte.

The interesting point to note is that for the two concentrations of CTAB and CPyCl in the preparation of emulsions the equi-creaming concentrations are found to be the same. Conclusion may, therefore, be drawn that creaming does not depend on the amount of the long chain ion employed for a *stable* emulsion.

The effect of electrolytes on the acceleration of the rate of creaming may be attributed to either or both of the following causes :

(a) Even after homogenization, the emulsion may contain oil droplets of various size and some of them may be very small. These very small droplets cream slowly and are the cause of the turbidity. Addition of an indifferent electrolyte in sufficient quantity affects the stability⁵ of these very small droplets first, brings about their flocculation to some extent and thus accelerates the rate of creaming.

(b) The diffuse part of the electrical double layer surrounding each oil droplet is distorted as the droplet moves upward (since liquids dispersed are chosen lighter than water) and the potential difference ("the sedimentation potential") thus generated opposes the upward movement of the oil droplets. Addition of an indifferent electrolyte lowers the potential of the diffuse double layer and also the "sedimentation potential" and thus accelerates the rate of creaming.

The polyvalent counter ions will be more effective than the univalent ions in both the cases (a) and (b) mentioned above. The concentration of the former required to produce a given rate of creaming will be much lower than that of the latter. This has actually been found.

Emulsions prepared by dispersing other liquids such as benzene, toluene and xylene (fraction boiling at 138.5° and is not definitely known whether it is a single isomer or mixtures of all the three isomers) in water and using CTAB or CPyCl as the stabilizer have been observed to behave similarly. The only difference is that the amount of the stabilizer needed to prepare the stable stock emulsions for investigation is comparatively high, often above the critical micelle concentration of the stabilizer used.

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